

LETTERS TO THE EDITOR

Packaging Geriatrics

Dear Editor,

Congratulations on your editorial. Can a rose by any other name smell as sweet? In 1994 a straw poll I carried out in a British Geriatrics Society conference bus identified over twenty different names for geriatrics! Is it we or our patients that dislike the name?

My case for geroconomy - the science of tending older people - is based upon a passionate belief that only by teaching the science of care of older people will we indeed reach the Nirvana of happiness in old age. The knowledge is vast and my ignorance is extensive.

The winds of change blowing through the UK National Health Service have transformed the very face of medicine. Open access to acute care for older people irrespective of age, sex, ethnic group and dependence is now the norm rather than the exception. Also, the majority of the Nightingale style long stay wards have been swept away and been replaced by personalised, single room accommodation. Yet, these benefits have been achieved at a price - consultant responsibility has been withdrawn from long stay care, consequently rehabilitation has suffered.

Warren's original hypothesis concerning consultant responsibility for long term care was based on the benefits to be gained from consultant leadership in the diagnosis and rehabilitation of the chronic sick. In 1943 Marjory Warren defined old age as being aged 60 and over, now we are discussing the medical care of the over eighties¹.

So I champion geroconomy by modifying the summary of Warren's article by changing the word chronic sick to age². Deep in our hearts, however we have changed, we know the truth and wisdom of your concluding remarks: "*Geriatric medicine begins where traditional medicine ends*".

I was delighted to read about the flourishing of the Hong Kong Geriatrics Society and the changing of the name from Geriatric [(loosely and facetiously by) ancient, worn-out past it] to Geriatrics-vibrant and alive³.

Our British society is flourishing too. Despite or because of the changes that have occurred, 95% of consultants specializing in the medical care of older people belong to the British Geriatrics Society.

Long may our two societies flourish: long may we continue the never ending task to make our world a better place for dependent older people to live in.

Yours sincerely,

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2. Millard PH. A case for the development of departments of geroconomy in all district general hospitals: discussion paper. *J Roy Soc Med* 1991;84:731-3.
3. *The Chambers Dictionary*, Chambers Harrap Publishers Ltd. 1993.

Editor's reply:

What's in a name....Geriatrics or not Geriatrics?

I thank you and all other geriatricians who have echoed to my editorial, and I express my sincere appreciation for their encouraging support.

"*What's in a name? That which we call a rose by any other name would smell as sweet?*"¹ Is geriatrics a rose? It depends on who smells it. "*To be (geriatrics), or not to be (geriatrics), that is the question...*"²

To discover a dancer's identity, one need only watch the dancer perform. A world made up of verbs and devoid of nouns, perplexing as it may be to some, finds a natural home in noncommutative geometry³, modern physics⁴ and eastern philosophy/religions⁵.

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1. Shakespeare W. *Romeo and Juliet* 1594:II,ii,43.
2. Shakespeare W. *Hamlet* 1605:III,i,56.
3. Mackenzie D. Through the looking glass. *The Sciences* 1997;37(3):32-37.
4. Zukav G. *The Dancing Wu Li Masters - An Overview of the New Physics*. London: Rider & Co 1979.

5. Fromm E. *The Art of Loving*. London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd. 1976:67-68.

Unexpected Life-Threatening Drug Interaction: Hypoglycaemia secondary to Anti-*Helicobacter pylori* Therapy

Dear Editor,

Ulcer syndrome and diabetes are both common in elderly people in Hong Kong. Detection of the causative agent *Helicobacter pylori*(Hp)¹ is essential for better cure of peptic ulcer. Unfortunately, we faced a patient suffering from dangerous hypoglycaemia secondary to oral hypoglycaemic agents and *Helicobacter Pylori* eradication combination.

A 78-year-old gentleman was admitted to hospital for diabetic control, he was maintained on glibenclamide 10mg om, 5mg noon and metformin 1g tds, as his sugar control improved after admission by better dietary restriction, with fasting/2hr haemoglucostix 8.1 and 11.5 mmol/l respectively. As he was found to be anaemic with haemoglobin of 9.8g/dl and iron saturation of 9% only, upper endoscopy was performed which showed multiple duodenal ulcers with positive rapid urease test. So one week course of amoxycillin 1g bd, omeprazole 20 mg bd, and clarithromycin 500mg bd was started. In subsequent two days, his haemoglucostix was progressively lower requiring reduction in dosage of glibenclamide until on day 3 post-endoscopy, his haemoglucostix was 0.9-1 mmol/l which persisted for one day despite all diabetic drugs were stopped, with confirmed blood glucose value as low as 1.6 mmol/l only. On direct questioning, he was found to have omitted meals because of poor appetite, which was attributed to the triple therapy. His diabetic drugs were slowly re-introduced and the original dosage resumed five days after the triple therapy.

Ulcer syndrome is common worldwide and has been related to *Helicobacter pylori* infection¹. As a result its detection indicates the need for eradication therapy². At present, the commonly prescribed drugs are triple therapy of omeprazole, amoxycillin and clarithromycin for one week, which is generally well tolerated except causing some nausea³.

Diabetes mellitus is also common in our ageing and affluent society, most of them being non-insulin-dependent diabetes on dietary restriction and

oral hypoglycaemic agents. As most of our patients are relatively old, their control is generally loose to prevent hypoglycaemic complications.

Often, the classic side-effects of appetite suppression, nausea and vomiting due to the high dosage of antibiotics were neglected, with most physicians stressed on compliance for successful eradication to prevent recurrence. Unfortunately, the combination of hypoglycaemic agents with markedly reduced calorie intake can result in dangerous hypoglycaemia. As most of upper endoscopy was done as out patients in Hong Kong, some of the hypoglycaemic complications may be missed. Elderly people living alone will be particularly vulnerable to such complications.

Although glibenclamide should be avoided in elderly diabetic patients due to its long half life, it is still one of the most commonly prescribed sulphonylureas, especially in the government general out patient clinics. We hope that our experience will alert our colleagues to avoid glibenclamide in elderly diabetics, particularly the prescription of two times daily dosage.

To conclude, all diabetic patients offered Hp eradication therapy should be warned of the potential side effects, with similar information dispatched to the relatives. Physicians should be prepared to reduce the dose of hypoglycaemic drugs at least temporarily when prescribing drugs that may suppress the appetite of patients.

Yours sincerely,

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